

Strengthening Gender Equality Across Institutions: Yellow Window and Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC) Leads Key On-Site Mentoring Visits at AGRIGEP Partner Universities

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In 2025, the AGRIGEP project marked an important milestone with two rounds of on-site mentoring focused on Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). Expert teams from Yellow Window (YW) and the Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC) visited the three widening country partner universities—MATE in Hungary, UP in Slovenia, and CZU in the Czech Republic—to support the co-creation and implementation of their GEPs. These strategic visits were part of the ongoing Horizon Europe-funded AGRIGEP project and brought renewed momentum to advancing gender equality in the institutions.

January 2025: Launch of Peer-Learning Exchange with Yellow Window

In January, Yellow Window consultants initiated their on-site engagements by visiting the MATE as the coordinating institution. This visit focused on the '7P Framework': theorising gender-based violence policies (UniSAFE project) – how universities can develop strategies preventing GBV and minimising the adverse effects of cases (both for the victims and the university's perspective).

The meetings were designed to stimulate reflection on institutional cultures and practices, facilitate open discussions with leadership and GEP implementation teams, and identify the GEP implementation status (data management system & data analysis; intersectional data analysis) of MATE at the same time.

There were two different workshops organised as part of the visit, the one focusing on Gender perspective on the Climate change and Circular Economy – specifically for PhD students and international students, and a second workshop on gender in research: how to integrate the gender perspective into research topics – for PI-s.

During the sessions, partner institution (MATE) shared its GEP implementation progress and challenges, with Yellow Window providing tailored feedback and recommendations grounded in their long-standing experience.

May and June 2025: Strategic Follow-Up and Capacity Building

The follow-up visits in **May 2025** served to build on the foundations laid in January. Over two intensive days — **May 26 and 30 and June 3-4** — the UPC team returned to MATE, UP, and CZU to deliver targeted support and strengthen institutional ownership of gender equality actions. Each visit included interactive workshops, in-depth discussions and intensive training on Gender Dimension in teaching, in research and Gender-Based Violence. These trainings were linked to the training material development of the project, which UPC leads as a mentor.

Forward Momentum

The AGRIGEP consortium — including mentoring partners Yellow Window, the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC), and the Association of Hungarian Women in Science (NATE) — remains committed to supporting widening partners in integrating gender equality into all levels of university life. These on-site visits have proven to be essential touchpoints in strengthening institutional capacity, enhancing mutual learning, and aligning efforts with Horizon Europe requirements.

The mentoring work continues in the second half of 2025 with additional mentoring activities on the development of institutions' GEP 2.0.

About AGRIGEP

The **AGRIGEP project** (HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01, Grant Agreement no. 101094158) supports structural change for gender equality in universities and research organisations in the field of agriculture and life sciences. Coordinated by the **Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE)**, the project brings together the **Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU)** and the **University of Primorska (UP)** as widening institutions, supported by mentoring partners **Yellow Window**, Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC), and Association of Hungarian Women in Science (NaTE).

AGRIGEP Beneficiaries:

WIDENING PARTNERS

- Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE), **Coordinator**
- Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU)
- University of Primorska (UP)

MENTORING PARTNERS

- Yellow Window (YW)
- Association of Hungarian Women in Science (NATE)
- Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - BarcelonaTech (UPC)

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